

ISic0280

I.Sicily inscription 0280

Language

Latin

Type

honorific

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Tauromenium

Place of origin (modern)

Taormina

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Taormina

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Aug(ustus) · pont(ifex) · max(imus) · trib(unicia) · pot(estate) · XI[---]

Apparatus

Text of CIL

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491490

EDCS 21900311

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. *Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum.* Berlin. At 10.6992 +add (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/buchseite/650752>)

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